

Health-Seeking Behavior, Medication-Taking Behavior, and Associated Factors Among Clients Visiting Community Pharmacies in Lagos State, South-West Nigeria

Promise Olaitan Ernest-Otaru

College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria

Tinuola Omotomilayo Odugbemi

College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria

Aloysius Obinna Ikwuka

College of Medicine and Health Sciences, American International University West Africa, Banjul, The Gambia

Francis Chigozie Udeh

College of Medicine and Health Sciences, American International University West Africa, Banjul, The Gambia

Abstract

Health is one of the most important aspects of human life, and man has since time immemorial been striving to maintain or restore good health in order to perform optimally. The existing high prevalence of the practice of self-medication, poor health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors encouraged by the constant display, advertisement, and accessibility to drugs in indiscriminate places, is a major determinant of the type, quantity, quality, effectiveness, and success of healthcare as they encourage irrational use of drugs and poor utilization of health facilities. This study aimed to assess the health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors of clients visiting community pharmacies in the Agege Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State, South-West Nigeria, and to identify the associated factors influencing these behaviors. A descriptive cross-sectional design, involving 305 clients selected from community pharmacies in the Agege LGA through a multi-stage stratified sampling method was used. Data collection was done using an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Data analysis was performed using SPSS (Version 23). The Chi-square test was employed to examine associations between socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics, with health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. The mean age of the study participants was 36.83 ± 11.89 years. Females, married people, Yorubas, and those who live with family members were more. Most of the study participants reside within the Agege LGA, have tertiary education, and are employed, but earn below US\$2 per day. Most of them had poor health-seeking behavior (56.7%), and also had poor medication-taking behavior (71.5%). A statistically significant relationship was observed between living status and health-seeking behavior ($p = 0.002$), with a higher proportion (46.8%) of those living with family exhibiting good health-seeking behavior compared to those who do not. The level of education ($p = 0.042$), employment status ($p = 0.049$), and income status ($p = 0.002$) had statistically significant association with medication-taking behavior. As community pharmacies serve as a crucial point of care for various health complaints, there is an urgent need to improve health-seeking and medication-taking behaviours among the population. Increased public awareness about the

More Information

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risks of self-medication, stricter regulations on drug sales and acquisition, and addressing the prevailing socio-economic challenges are highly recommended.

Introduction

The constant interactions between the human body interphase and the social, physical, biological, and chemical environment determine the state of health of an individual [58]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), health is a state of complete wholeness and not just the mere absence of disease, illness or infirmity. It includes being healthy physically, mentally, and socially [74]. The ability to enjoy the highest attainable standard of health is one of the most important fundamental rights of every human being regardless of race, religion, political belief, economic or social condition [74]. Therefore, it is paramount that an individual seek health to improve the quality of life.

It is common for an individual to feel unwell at any point in life. The innate survival instinct creates the tendency for a human to seek health. Health-seeking behaviour (HSB) is the practice of finding an appropriate and most suitable remedy by individuals who perceive themselves to be ill or experiencing a health problem [53]. Health-seeking behavior is also referred to as sick-term behavior or illness behavior. On a broader scope of concept, HSB encompasses activities undertaken to ensure and maintain good health, prevent ill health, promote good health, as well as address any deviance from a good health state [43].

Globally, people daily, irrespective of their level of education, seek health with or without consulting a doctor. The majority practice what is known as self-care, which is any action taken for one's physical, mental, and emotional well-being. It includes regular exercise, relaxing after a stressful day, eating a balanced diet, and treatment of minor illnesses requiring minimal supervision from healthcare professionals. Self-care is often practiced because of its perceived convenience, lower cost, and time-saving. It is a lifelong habit, and culture, which involves self-medication. This practice is also seen among Nigerians [40].

Self-medication is a practice many indulge in, to seek health. Self-medication has been defined as the act of selecting and using drugs/medicines by individuals to treat self-diagnosed illnesses or symptoms, or the intermittent or continued use of a drug prescribed for chronic or recurrent disease or symptoms [73]. Self-medication could be a safe and responsible practice only when practised for minor symptoms like headaches, heartburn, etc, in which over-the-counter (OTC) medications are recommended. It is expected that health conditions considered serious or in which medical expertise is required should be presented to a doctor for a proper diagnosis and medical

recommendations on the prescription-only medication (POM) needed, or to consult a pharmacist if the medicine needed is a pharmacy-only medicine (PO) [5]. Irresponsible self-medication includes the uncontrolled use of herbs and the retention, and re-use of POM without the input of a doctor or physician [3]. Often times, many individuals practice irresponsible and potentially dangerous self-prescription by obtaining POMs without consulting a physician for proper recommendation/prescription [37]. This practice is common globally in both developed and developing countries [11, 12], and may be more common than even prescribed medications [41].

The nature and extent of the practice of self-medication varies in different cultural contexts. It cuts across culture, gender, age, occupation, income, race, place of residence, religion, and socio-medical factors. Factors such as poor diagnostic ability together with limited skill in appropriate management have resulted in an increased rate of self-medication and lowered the rate of utilization of healthcare facilities [62]. Other factors encouraging this practice include long waiting periods in hospitals [44], high cost [1], lack of accessibility [46], shortage of healthcare physicians, or certain perceptions that the ailment is beyond the knowledge of western trained physicians [13].

In the average Nigerian thought, visit to a community pharmacy is often chosen over a hospital visit due to cost implication, ease, and quick response. This idea makes most urban community settlers seeking healthcare often visit community pharmacies. However, visiting a community pharmacy is still not a frequent occurrence in some developed countries like England [10], even as it is known that pharmacies play a crucial role in addressing various health complaints. Moreover, drugs of various pharmacological classes are easily accessible and often sold by unauthorized vendors in unauthorized locations like roadside stalls, open markets, commuter buses, and motor parks in the Agege LGA and other developing urban areas, leading to widespread misinformation about their clinical indications, and contributing to widespread drug misuse [72].

The pre-existing practice of indulging in irresponsible and potentially dangerous self-medication of prescription-only medications is increasingly becoming a serious concern to health care globally [40]. The factors influencing health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors of Agege residents are still not well understood. These gaps in knowledge can hinder the effective utilization of community pharmacies as a resource for healthcare, potentially leading to

suboptimal health outcomes. This present study, therefore, aimed to explore the associated factors influencing health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors among clients visiting community pharmacies within the Agege LGA, to identify barriers to accessing healthcare, and to highlight successful interventions.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study took place in the Agege Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State, located in South-West Nigeria. Agege boasts a bustling economy with numerous urban markets, approximately 35 community pharmacies, and a projected population of 683,600 [8]. Across Agege and Ifako-Ijaiye LGAs in Lagos State, there are an estimated 150 community pharmacies, each serving around 30 patients daily [45].

Study Design

A six-week community-based cross-sectional survey was carried out to examine the health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors among clients visiting community pharmacies within the Agege LGA. Data was collected using an interviewer-administered questionnaire.

Study Population

The study focused on clients visiting community pharmacies within the Agege LGA. According to a previous census, the population of residents aged 15 and above in the area was recorded at 307,677 [8].

Sample Size

A sample size of 305 was calculated from the study population using the Cochran formula for a single proportion formula,

$$n = \frac{z^2 PQ}{d^2} \tag{1}$$

n agreement with previous studies [49, 50, 51, 52, 60].

Where:

n = minimum sample size for a study population greater than 10,000.

Z = standard normal deviation set at 1.96, corresponding to a 95% confidence interval, as per standard statistical table of normal distribution.

P = proportion of the study population visiting community pharmacies, estimated at 85% (0.85) from a similar study among adult traders in the Agege LGA, with a response rate of 40% [1].

Q = 1 – P = 1 – 0.85 = 0.15

d = degree of accuracy desired (absolute precision) = 5.0% = 0.05

Using the formula:

$$n_0 = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.85 \times 0.15}{0.05^2} = 195.9 \approx 196$$

To account for potential non-response, the calculated minimum sample size was adjusted by considering a 40% non-response rate, as seen in a previous study [1]. This adjustment accounts for factors such as incomplete questionnaires, participant dropout, or data loss. Ultimately, the sample size was finalized at 327 study participants to ensure the study’s reliability. Thus, in adjusting the estimated minimum sample size for non-response and attrition:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{\text{expected response rate}} = \frac{196}{0.6} = 326.667 \sim 327 \text{ sample size}$$

From the calculated sample size, 305 individuals who consented to participate were selected using a multi-stage stratified sampling approach. Five wards (Isale/Idimangoro, Orile Agege, Darocha, Keke, and Okekoto) were randomly chosen from the eleven wards in the Agege LGA. In each ward, three community pharmacies were randomly selected, resulting in a total of fifteen pharmacies visited over a six-week data collection period.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Male and female adults, resident and non-resident clients visiting community pharmacies in the Agege LGA were included in the study. Health professionals including medical doctors, nurses, and pharmacists currently working in other healthcare facilities and patent medicine vendors within the Agege LGA were excluded in the study.

Data Collection

Data for this study were collected using one-on-one interviewer-administered Google Form questionnaires. The self-developed tool included 26 questions, primarily closed-ended with a few open-ended items adapted from existing literature. The questionnaire was piloted before use to evaluate health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors of study participants. Each questionnaire has 3 sections: 1. Socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the study participants; 2. health-seeking behavior of the study participants; and 3. medication-taking behavior of the study participants.

An uninterrupted, designated area within the pharmacy was set up for conducting interviews. Clients who visited the pharmacies during the six-week survey period and agreed to participate were selected using a stratified random sampling method. Approximately 50 questionnaires were administered each week, with individuals being approached every 20 minutes based on the flow of clients into the pharmacy. Only a member of the research team was involved in administering and filling out the questionnaires on Google Forms. Upon successful data collection, questionnaires were cross-checked for adequacy of

information, numbered, organized, and entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet for data analysis.

Reliability of Data Collection

A pre-test of the data collection tool (questionnaire) was conducted with 30 clients (approximately 10% of the sample size) at two community pharmacies in a different LGA (Ikeja), in Lagos State. Some questions were subsequently revised for clarity. The test-retest reliability of the data was assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient. A Pearson correlation coefficient (r) greater than 0.7 was obtained, was deemed sufficient to validate the use of the research methodology, as a value of 0.7 is considered the minimum for good test-retest reliability [38].

Data Analysis

The data was validated and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 software. A 5% significance level (p-value) was considered statistically significant. The socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the study participants, along with their responses, were presented in frequencies and percentages. Information about health-seeking and medication-taking behaviours of the study participants was documented and compared across age groups and income status. Bivariate analysis using Chi-square was performed to assess the association between the independent

variables (socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics) and the dependent variables (health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH). A letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Community Health and Primary Care in the College of Medicine, University of Lagos and this letter was presented to community pharmacies to seek permission from the related authorities of the community pharmacies which were involved in the study. The interviewer properly informed the participants of the nature of the study, its objectives, its confidentiality, its importance to the society, and an informed oral consent was obtained from all study participants. There were no financial benefits to the study participants. The participants were also assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time during the data collection stage without suffering any consequence if they choose not to participate further.

Results

305 individuals voluntarily participated in this study, giving a 93.3% response rate of the proposed sample size of 327. The following tables represent the results obtained in this study.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Age group (years)	
< 20	6 (2.0)
20 - 24	21 (6.9)
25 - 29	73 (23.9)
30 - 34	64 (21.0)
35 - 39	47 (15.4)
40 - 44	24 (7.9)
45 - 49	19 (6.2)
50 - 54	18 (5.9)
55 - 59	14 (4.6)
≥60	19 (6.2)
Mean ± SD	36.83 ± 11.89
Gender	
Male	138 (45.2)
Female	166 (54.4)
Transgender	1 (0.3)
Marital status	
Single	93 (30.5)
Married	201 (65.9)
Separated	6 (2.0)
Widowed	5 (1.6)
Ethnicity	
Yoruba	202 (66.2)
Igbo	41 (13.4)
Hausa	33 (10.8)

Others	29 (9.5)
Living status	
With family	252 (82.6)
Alone	40 (13.1)
With non-family	13 (4.3)

The mean age of the study participants was 36.83±11.89 years, with the majority being young adults within the age group of 25-44. Most of the study participants were female (54.4%). A significant

proportion (65.9%) were married, and the majority (66.2%) were of the Yoruba ethnic group. In addition, 82.6% of the study participants live with their family members.

Table 2: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Highest level of education completed	
None	12 (3.9)
Vocational	27 (8.9)
Primary	8 (2.6)
Secondary	83 (27.2)
Tertiary	175 (57.4)
Employment status	
Employed	
Self-employed	139 (45.6)
Private employed	89 (29.2)
Government employed	30 (9.8)
Unemployed	
Student	26 (8.5)
Retired	12 (3.9)
Unemployed (due to lack of job)	9 (3.0)
Estimated monthly income in Naira (₦)	
<₦10,000	10 (3.3)
₦10,000 – ₦30,000	12 (3.9)
₦30,001 – ₦50,000	51 (16.7)
₦50,001 – ₦100,000	131 (43.0)
₦100,001 – ₦200,000	73 (23.9)
₦200,001 – ₦500,000	20 (6.6)
>₦500,000	8 (2.6)
LGA of residence in Lagos State	
Agege	274 (89.9)
Ifako-Ijaiye	12 (3.9)
Alimosho	8 (2.6)
Ojodu	5 (1.6)
Ota	2 (0.7)
Surulere	1 (0.3)
Eti-Osa	1 (0.3)
Ikeja	1 (0.3)
Isolo	1 (0.3)

Most of the study participants (89.8%) lived within the Agege LGA of Lagos State, had completed tertiary education (57.4%), and were employed (84.6%). A significant portion (66.9%) earned less than US\$2 per

day, with 7.2% earning below the current minimum wage of 30,000 naira, set by the Federal Government of Nigeria as of the time of conducting this study.

Table 3: Health-seeking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Ever visited a community pharmacy	
Yes	305 (100)

Reason for current visit to the community pharmacy	
Self	232 (76.1)
Third party	86 (28.2)
Age group of the third party (n=86)	
> 5 years	21 (24.4)
5-9 years	25 (29.1)
10-19 years	7 (8.1)
20-64 years	17 (19.8)
≥65 years	16 (18.6)
Presence of illness in the study participant or third party	
Yes	299 (98.0)
No	6 (2.9)
Sought medical advice before coming to the pharmacy (n=299)	
Yes	238 (79.6)
No	16 (5.4)
Not Applicable	45 (15.1)
Person consulted for medical advice (n=238)	
Health provider	150 (63.0)
Family and health provider	27 (11.3)
Others (drug hawkers, patent drug vendors, etc)	21 (8.8)
Health provider and traditional practitioner	15 (6.3)
Health provider, family, and traditional practitioner	12 (5.0)
Family and friends	9 (3.8)
Traditional practitioner	4 (1.7)
Received treatment before coming to the pharmacy (n=299)	
Yes	249 (83.3)
No	50 (16.7)
Type of treatment received before coming to the pharmacy (n=249)	
Orthodox treatment only	168 (67.5)
Combination of orthodox and traditional treatment	57 (22.9)
Self-care (inhalation, massage, etc)	18 (7.2)
Traditional treatment only	6 (2.4)
Health-seeking for minor symptoms (sore throat, headache, etc)	
Visit a doctor/nurse	50 (16.4)
Visit a pharmacist	117 (38.4)
Self-care (non-pharmacological)	15 (4.9)
Get OTC drugs from hawkers/patent medicine store	116 (38.0)
Take herbs	7 (2.3)
Health-seeking for major diseases (Diabetes mellitus, STI, UTI, hypertension, cancer, etc)	
Visit a doctor/nurse	274 (89.8)
Visit a pharmacist	19 (6.2)
Get OTC drugs from hawkers/patent medicine store	7 (2.3)
Take herbs	5 (1.6)

Every study participant had earlier visited a community pharmacy at one point or the other. The majority of the study participants 232 (76.1%) were at the pharmacy to seek care for themselves, while only 86 (28.2%) were there to seek care for someone else. The majority of the third parties 46 (53.5%) were children below 10 years of age. The majority of the study participants 299 (98.0%) were in the pharmacy due to the presence of symptom or disease either in themselves or in the third party which they care for. The majority 238 (79.6%)

have also sought medical advice, and had received treatment before coming to the pharmacy 249 (83.3%). In addition, the majority 150 (63.0%) sought medical advice from health providers, and 168 (67.5%) received orthodox treatment only, before pharmacy visits. The majority of the study participants reported that they would visit a pharmacist 117 (38.4%) or get OTC drugs from hawkers or patent medicine store 116 (38.0%) if they have a minor symptom. The majority 274 (89.8%)

reported that they would visit a doctor or nurse if they have a major disease. The majority of the study participants 173 (56.7%) had a poor health-seeking behavior.

Table 4: Overall Health-seeking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Good	132 (43.3)
Poor	173 (56.7)

Table 5: Medication-taking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Frequency of self-medicating per year	
Never	65 (21.3)
1-2 times	159 (52.1)
3-4 times	47 (15.4)
More than 4 times	34 (11.2)
Reasons for taking antibiotics	
Whenever it is prescribed	233 (76.4)
Whenever I feel I have an infection	163 (53.4)
Whenever I treat malaria	28 (9.2)
Behavior while taking antibiotics	
Take as prescribed (frequency and duration)	159 (52.1)
Stop taking it once I feel better	118 (38.7)
Change frequency of use to suit my schedule	28 (9.2)
Medication-taking behavior	
Take as advised by the doctor/pharmacist	263 (86.2)
Take as was used for a similar symptom/disease	72 (23.6)
As advised by relatives, friends, and media	38 (12.5)
Handling of drugs remaining after treatment	
Keep it for use at another time	250 (82.0)
I usually finish my drugs	4 (1.3)
Give it to a friend or relative with a similar symptom	38 (12.5)
Discard it in the refuse dump or flush it in the toilet	13 (4.3)

Most study participants (78.7%) reported a history of self-medication, with 52.1% practicing it 1-2 times per year. In addition, the majority (76.4%) indicated they take antibiotics only when prescribed. However, a significant portion (53.4%) admitted to using antibiotics whenever they suspected an infection. A large number (52.1%) follow prescribed dosages while taking antibiotics, with 86.2% adhering to advice from doctors or pharmacists. Furthermore, 82.0% keep leftover medications after treatment for future use.

Table 6: Overall Medication-taking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	n (%)
Good	87 (28.5)
Poor	218 (71.5)

The majority of the study participants (71.5%) had a poor medication-taking behavior, whereas only 28.5% had a good medication-taking behavior.

Table 7: Association between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Health-seeking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	Good health-seeking behavior n=132	Poor health-seeking behavior n=173	X ²	df	Fisher's exact p-value
Age group (years)			4.576	9	0.870
< 20	3 (50.0%)	3 (50.0%)			
20 – 24	9 (42.9%)	12 (57.1%)			
25 – 29	26 (35.6%)	47 (64.4%)			
30 – 34	28 (43.8%)	36 (56.3%)			

35 – 39	19 (40.4%)	28 (59.6%)			
40 – 44	12 (50.0%)	12 (50.0%)			
45 – 49	11 (57.9%)	8 (42.1%)			
50 – 54	9 (50.0%)	9 (50.0%)			
55 – 59	6 (42.9%)	8 (57.1%)			
≥60	9 (47.4%)	10 (52.6%)			
Gender			2.160	2	0.340
Male	65 (47.1%)	73 (52.9%)			
Female	67 (40.4%)	99 (59.6%)			
Transgender	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)			
Marital Status			7.322	3	0.062
Single	30 (32.3%)	63 (67.7%)			
Married	98 (48.8%)	103 (51.2%)			
Separated	2 (33.3%)	4 (66.7%)			
Widowed	2 (40.0%)	3 (60.0%)			
Ethnicity			1.854	3	0.603
Yoruba	85 (42.1%)	117 (57.9%)			
Igbo	17 (41.5%)	24 (58.5%)			
Hausa	14 (42.4%)	19 (57.6%)			
Others	16 (55.2%)	13 (44.8%)			
Living Status			12.327	2	0.002**
Living with family	118 (46.8%)	134 (53.2%)			
Alone	14 (35.0%)	26 (65.0%)			
Living with non-family	0 (0.0%)	13 (100.0%)			

Note: **Statistically significant (Fisher’s exact); X²–Chi squared; df-degree of freedom; p-value <0.05

No statistically significant association was found between socio-demographic characteristics and health-seeking behavior of the study participants, except for living status ($p=0.002$), with 46.8% of those living with family exhibiting good health-seeking behavior

compared to 53.2% of those with poor health-seeking behavior. Notably, every study participant living with non-family members demonstrated a poor health-seeking behavior.

Table 8: Association between Socio-Economic Characteristics and Health-seeking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	Good health-seeking behavior $n=132$	Poor health-seeking behavior $n=173$	X ²	Df	Fisher’s exact p-value
Level of education completed			3.481	4	0.481
None	6 (50.0%)	6 (50.0%)			
Vocational	8 (29.6%)	19 (70.4%)			
Primary	4 (50.0%)	4 (50.0%)			
Secondary	33 (39.8%)	50 (60.2%)			
Tertiary	81 (46.3%)	94 (53.7%)			
Employment Status			0.282	1	0.595
Employed	110 (42.6%)	148 (57.4%)			
Unemployed	22 (46.8%)	25 (53.2%)			
Estimated Monthly Income			4.462	4	0.347
< N30,000	12 (54.5%)	10 (45.5%)			
N30,001 – N50,000	18 (35.3%)	33 (64.7%)			
N50,001 – N100,000	61 (46.6%)	70 (53.4%)			
N100,001 – N200,000	32 (43.8%)	41 (56.2%)			
>N200,001 – N500,000	9 (32.1%)	19 (67.9%)			

Note: X²–Chi-squared; df-degree of freedom; p-value <0.05

There was no statistically significant association between the socio-economic characteristics and health-seeking behavior of the study participants.

However, majority of the study participants with tertiary level of education (53.7%) and the employed (57.4%) had a poor health-seeking behavior.

Table 9: Association between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Medication-taking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	Good medication-taking behavior <i>n</i> =87	Poor medication-taking behavior <i>n</i> =218	X ²	df	Fisher's exact <i>p</i> -value
Age group (years)			7.529	9	0.582
< 20	4 (66.7%)	2 (33.3%)			
20 – 24	8 (38.1%)	13 (61.9%)			
25 – 29	17 (23.3%)	56 (76.7%)			
30 – 34	18 (28.1%)	46 (71.9%)			
35 – 39	12 (25.5%)	35 (74.5%)			
40 – 44	8 (33.3%)	16 (66.7%)			
45 – 49	6 (31.6%)	13 (68.4%)			
50 – 54	4 (22.2%)	14 (77.8%)			
55 – 59	5 (35.7%)	9 (64.3%)			
≥60	5 (26.3%)	14 (73.7%)			
Gender			0.417	2	0.812
Male	40 (29.0%)	98 (71.0%)			
Female	47 (28.3%)	119 (71.7%)			
Transgender	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)			
Marital Status			2.534	3	0.469
Single	28 (30.1%)	65 (69.9%)			
Married	58 (28.9%)	143 (71.1%)			
Separated	1 (16.7%)	5 (83.3%)			
Widowed	0 (0.0%)	5 (100.0%)			
Ethnicity			0.488	3	0.922
Yoruba	58 (28.7%)	144 (71.3%)			
Igbo	10 (24.4%)	31 (75.6%)			
Hausa	10 (30.3%)	23 (69.7%)			
Others	9 (31.0%)	20 (69.0%)			
Living Status			3.084	2	0.214
Living with family	77 (30.6%)	175 (69.4%)			
Alone	7 (17.5%)	33 (82.5%)			
Living with non-family	3 (23.1%)	10 (76.9%)			

Note: X²-Chi squared; df-degree of freedom; *p*-value <0.05

There was no statistically significant association between the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants and their medication-taking behavior, as all variables had a *p*-value >0.05. However, 30.6% of the study participants who live with family had

a good medication-taking behavior compared to those who live alone (17.5%). Moreover, a good medication-taking behavior is almost similar among male (29.0%) and female (28.3%) study participants.

Table 10: Association between Socio-Economic Characteristics and Medication-taking Behavior of the Study Participants

Variable	Good medication-taking behavior <i>n</i> =87	Poor medication-taking behavior <i>n</i> =218	X ²	df	Fisher's exact <i>p</i> -value
Level of education completed			9.885	4	0.042**
None	5 (41.7%)	7 (58.3%)			
Vocational	4 (14.8%)	23 (85.2%)			
Primary	2 (25.0%)	6 (75.0%)			
Secondary	16 (19.3%)	67 (80.7%)			
Tertiary	60 (34.3%)	115 (65.7%)			

Employment Status			3.860	1	0.049**
Employed	68 (26.4%)	190 (73.6%)			
Unemployed	19 (40.4%)	28 (59.6%)			
Estimated Monthly Income			17.473	4	0.002**
< N30,000	12 (54.5%)	10 (45.5%)			
N30,001 – N50,000	10 (19.6%)	41 (80.4%)			
N50,001 – N100,000	27 (20.6%)	104 (79.4%)			
N100,001 – N200,000	27 (37.0%)	46 (63.0%)			
>N200,001 – N500,000	11 (39.3%)	17 (60.7%)			

**Statistically significant (Fisher’s exact); X²–Chi-squared; df-degree of freedom; p-value <0.05

There was a statistically significant association between socio-economic characteristics of the study participants and their medication-taking behaviour, for example, level of education completed ($p=0.042$), employment status ($p=0.049$), and estimated monthly income ($p=0.002$). A higher proportion of the study participants (41.7%) who were uneducated had a good medication-taking behavior compared to those who were educated. Likewise, a higher proportion of the unemployed (40.4%) had a good medication-taking behavior compared to the employed (26.4%). In addition, those who earned below 30,000 naira (Nigeria’s minimum wage as of the time of conducting this study) had a good medication-taking behavior compared to those who earned more. In general, many of the study participants had a poor medication-taking behavior irrespective of their socio-economic status.

Discussion

The mean age of the study participants was 36.83±11.89 years, and indicated a predominance of adults aged 25-39, in contrast to another study where teenagers and young adults (18-29 years) were more prevalent [48]. This adult predominance may stem from their independence and active pursuit of livelihoods [39, 47], which exposes them to stressors that often result in ailments, leading to frequent visits to community pharmacies for treatment. Increased stress can lead to mutation which is an alteration in the DNA sequence of an organism giving rise to new alleles [29]. Linked to the induction of oxidative stress are major free radicals. Among these major free radicals, superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and hydroperoxyl radicals are of physiological significance. A non-radical of physiological significance is hydrogen peroxide [28]. The slight female majority (54.4%) aligns with global patterns showing women are more likely to engage in healthcare services compared to men [4, 9]. Meanwhile, the negligible transgender representation reflects Nigeria’s societal dynamics, where transgender individuals face marginalization, often resulting in underreporting in surveys.

The high proportion of married participants (65.9%) underscores the cultural importance of marriage in the Nigerian society. Similarly, the predominance of study participants from the Yoruba ethnic group (66.2%)

corresponds to this present study’s location in Lagos State, a region largely inhabited by the Yoruba ethnic group [51, 52]. Furthermore, 82.6% of the study participants live with their family which underscores the significant role of family in shaping healthcare complaints and perceptions, consistent with the finding in another study [54].

A significant majority (89.9%) of the study participants reside within the Agege LGA, reflecting the study’s targeted sampling in this area. Educational attainment is notable, with over half (57.4%) having completed tertiary education. This aligns with the reputation of Lagos State as an educational hub, which likely influences lifestyles and subsequently, the health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors of the study participants.

The health-seeking behavior of the study participants was graded as either good or poor. The grade was out of 4 based on the following considerations: the person from whom the study participant sought medical advice when ill, the type of treatment sought or received, the behavior of the study participant towards minor symptoms, and the behavior of the study participant towards major diseases.

The majority of the study participants visited community pharmacies due to illness, either for themselves (76.1%) or on behalf of a third party (28.2%), most commonly for children under 10 years old (53.5%). This highlights the role of family and social networks in health-seeking behavior, where individuals often act as healthcare decision-makers for others, particularly children. Notably, a significant proportion of the study participants had already sought medical advice (79.6%) or treatment (83.3%) prior to their community pharmacy visit, indicating that community pharmacies frequently serve as a secondary step in the healthcare process, often for follow-up care or medication acquisition.

For minor symptoms such as sore throat, headache, etc, many chose to visit a pharmacist (38.4%) or purchase OTC medicines from drug hawkers or patent medicine stores (38.0%). In contrast, for major diseases such as diabetes mellitus, sexually transmitted infection (STI), urinary tract infection (UTI), hypertension, cancer, etc, the majority (89.8%)

preferred consulting a doctor or a nurse. This behavior demonstrates a clear distinction in how individuals address health conditions, with community pharmacies being a primary resource for less severe health problems.

Metabolic disorders, e.g. Hypertension, Adiposity, Diabetes mellitus and Dyslipidemia, collectively known as Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs) are diseases related to one another [15, 16, 18, 33, 35, 36, 63]. Different studies have shown that MSDs are associated with asymptomatic hyperuricemia, systemic immune inflammatory processes, and fibrogenesis all of which can lead to nephropathy [19, 20, 23, 24, 25, 30, 32, 34, 64, 65, 66, 67, 71]. Obesity (adiposity) is also a risk factor for non-Hodgkin lymphoma [27].

Among the socio-demographic characteristics, there was a statistically significant relationship between living status and health-seeking behavior, with study participants living with family exhibiting better health-seeking practices (46.8%) than those living alone (35.0%). This aligns with studies showing that social support systems, such as family, positively influence healthcare decisions. Similarly, married study participants displayed a better health-seeking behavior (48.8%) compared to those who were single (32.3%). However, other socio-demographic characteristics such as age group, gender, marital status, and ethnicity did not show any statistically significant associations with health-seeking behavior, suggesting that poor health-seeking behavior is widespread across different population groups.

Among the socio-economic characteristics, it is concerning that a majority of the study participants with tertiary education (53.7%) and those employed (57.4%) exhibited poor health-seeking behavior. This suggests that even individuals with higher education and stable employment may underutilize healthcare services, potentially due to factors such as time constraints, self-medication, or a lack of perceived necessity.

The medication-taking behavior of the study participants was graded as either good or poor. The grade was out of 4 based on the following considerations: history of self-medication, frequency of self-medication per year, rational use of antibiotics plus other drugs, and handling of remaining drugs after treatment.

The study identified a high prevalence of self-medication (78.7%), with over half (52.1%) practicing it 1-2 times per year. This trend is particularly alarming given the frequent use of antibiotics without prescriptions (53.4%), which significantly increases the risk of antibiotic resistance. Factors such as the ease of medication access and economic constraints likely drive this behavior.

No statistically significant relationship was found between socio-demographic characteristics and medication-taking behavior, indicating that poor medication-taking behavior is widespread across various groups. However, those living with family demonstrated a better medication-taking behavior (30.6%) compared to those living alone (17.5%), suggesting a positive influence of family on health-related practices.

It is very interesting to note that a statistically significant association was observed between all socio-economic characteristics variables and medication-taking behavior. Interestingly, study participants without formal education (41.7%), those unemployed (40.4%), and individuals earning below the minimum wage of 30,000 naira (54.5%) were more likely to exhibit good medication-taking behavior. This finding suggests that adherence to proper medication use may depend less on resources and access to information, and more on individual habits and underlying factors. Nevertheless, the overall prevalence of poor medication-taking behavior (71.5%) underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to educate the public about the risks of improper medicine use, particularly regarding the importance of completing antibiotic courses and avoiding self-medication. Faulty drug-handling practices were also prevalent, aligning with findings from another study [55].

Nevertheless, metabolic syndrome diseases (MSDs) are interrelated diseases with very high economic costs, morbidity, and mortality rates, thus requiring the search for new and effective treatment options [36]. Treatment optimization in MSD patients using a combination of HMG-CoA and SGLT-2 inhibitors, and A2RB (AT1) has resultant clinical effectiveness as indicated by marked improvements in metabolic functions of the heart, liver, pancreas, and kidney [17, 21, 22, 31, 36, 68, 69, 70]. In addition, Glucagon-like Peptide 1 Receptor Agonists (GLP-1 RAs) e.g. Liraglutide have been found to improve the efficacy of treatment and clinical course of type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension in patients with such comorbidities [26]. During interviews, many study participants voiced concerns about rising medication costs due to the Nigeria's economic downturn. They described challenges in affording prescriptions, often purchasing smaller quantities of prescribed medications and returning later for additional doses. This practice raises concerns about poor medication adherence, sub-therapeutic dosing, suboptimal clinical outcomes, and the potential exacerbation of antibiotic resistance for example.

Factors Associated with Health-seeking Behavior of the Study Participants

The findings from this present study reveal several key factors influencing health-seeking and medication-

taking behaviors. These behaviors are shaped by a complex interplay of living conditions, marital status, socio-economic factors, and overall awareness of health practices.

One of the most significant findings in this present study is the association between living status and health-seeking behavior. The study participants living with family exhibited a better health-seeking behavior compared to those living alone. This suggests that family dynamics play a crucial role in encouraging and facilitating access to healthcare services. Family members may act as caregivers, provide emotional support, or even influence the decision to seek medical attention, particularly for those who might otherwise delay or avoid seeking care. This finding is supported by the report of a different study which stated that humans are guided in healthcare decisions by past experiences, family and friends, social networks, cultural beliefs, customs, tradition, professional knowledge, and intuition [14, 61].

Marital status further amplifies this trend, with a higher proportion of the married study participants showing a good health-seeking behavior compared to their single counterparts. This could be attributed to the shared responsibility within a marriage, where healthcare decisions are often jointly made, and the presence of a partner may provide additional motivation to seek timely medical attention.

Interestingly, the severity of the health condition significantly impacts the choice of healthcare services. The study participants visited community pharmacies for minor symptoms such as sore throat, headache, etc, but preferred to consult doctors or nurses for more serious conditions like diabetes mellitus, STI, UTI, hypertension, cancer, etc, supporting the report of another study [56]. This dichotomy reflects a common perception that community pharmacies are more appropriate for managing minor symptoms, while more severe or chronic medical conditions necessitate a professional medical consultation.

Despite these trends, this present study found no statistically significant association between socio-economic characteristics (such as level of education, employment status, and estimated monthly income) and health-seeking behavior. This suggests that poor health-seeking behavior is pervasive across different socio-economic groups, indicating a broader issue within the community's approach to healthcare. This finding is in contrast to the findings of another study [42].

Factors Associated with Medication-taking Behavior of the Study Participants

Medication-taking behavior was heavily influenced by the practice of self-medication, with a high prevalence rate of 78.7%. Self-medication was often chosen as a response to minor health issues, apparently due to the

easy availability of medications, and perceived economic benefits. This finding is concerning, as self-medication, particularly with antibiotics, can lead to inappropriate use and contribute to the growing problem of antibiotic resistance.

A significant proportion of the study participants reported taking antibiotics whenever they suspected an infection, even without a prescription. This practice underscores a lack of awareness about the dangers of improper antibiotic use, suggesting an urgent need for public health interventions focused on educating the populace about the risks associated with such behavior. Similar to health-seeking behavior, living status also played a role in medication-taking behavior. Those living with family (30.6%) were more likely to exhibit a good medication-taking behavior compared to those living alone (17.5%). This again highlights the supportive role of family members in monitoring and encouraging adherence to proper medication regimens.

Socio-economic characteristics were also found to be significantly associated with medication-taking behavior. Study participants with tertiary education, stable employment, and higher income were more likely to demonstrate a poor medication-taking behavior, in contrast to other studies which reported that drug adherence is low among people with low educational background, and tertiary education was associated with higher adherence therefore proposed an improved education to promote drug adherence [6, 75]. It was also reported that employed status of an individual is positively associated with medication adherence [75]. With regards to the income status, the report of a different study which reported that there is a positive association between income status and medication adherence [59], is in contrast to the finding of this present study.

However, the finding of this present study agrees with the finding of another study which reported a negative association between higher education and drug adherence [2], and the report of another study where highly employed individuals were less likely to be adherent to drug prescription than non-employed individuals [57, 59]. Notably, the result in this present study is similar to the report of another study where a negative association between higher income and medication adherence was found [7].

The inverse proportionality of the socio-economic variables could be related to the fact that greater access to resources, healthcare information, and a better understanding of the importance of drug adherence is not directly proportional to better health behavior. While socio-economic factors are influential, they are not the sole determinants of good medication-taking behavior. The overall poor medication-taking behavior observed in 71.5% of the study participants,

regardless of their socio-economic status, points to a gap in health education and awareness. This suggests that public health campaigns need to be more effective in reaching and educating the population about the importance of following prescribed medication regimens, the risks of self-medication, and the dangers of antibiotic misuse.

Conclusion

Living status and marital status significantly influenced health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors, with those living with family and married individuals exhibiting better practices. Socio-economic factors, such as higher education, stable employment, and income status do not correlate with good medication-taking behavior. As community pharmacies serve as a crucial point of care for various health complaints, there is an urgent need to improve health-seeking and medication-taking behaviors among the population by enhancing public awareness about the risks of self-medication, stricter regulations on drug sales and acquisition, and addressing the prevailing socio-economic challenges in the society.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that they do not have any possible conflicts of interest.

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